

Utilizing Large Language Models to Detect Contradictions in a Medical Case Report

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Introduction

Large language models (LLMs) are generative artificial intelligence (AI) systems that have demonstrated promise in producing structured medical data, including clinical documentation such as SOAP notes (Keerthana et al.; Kupferschmidt et al.; Kimura et al.). Beyond documentation tasks, LLMs are increasingly being evaluated across a range of medical applications to assess their linguistic competence and problem-solving capabilities (Chimirri et al.). In clinical genetics, for example, neuro-symbolic question-answering models have been proposed to automate pedigree analysis for hereditary cancer risk assessment (Lundgren et al.). However, others have argued that many state-of-the-art LLMs remain limited by insufficient hierarchical knowledge representation, particularly with respect to visual structures and well-established biological taxonomies (Tan et al.; Williams et al.).

Medical literature and clinical documentation may contain internal inconsistencies. A temporal publication analysis demonstrated steady growth in the body of literature addressing medical errors (Atanasov et al.). Among 12,415 publications related to medical errors, the earliest dated to 1961; the number of publications increased over time, exceeding 1,000 by 2003 and 10,000 by 2017 (Atanasov et al.). In clinical practice, geneticists and other healthcare professionals routinely encounter incomplete information and contradictory data in medical records and published reports. Yet such discrepancies can be difficult to detect. In one survey study, 260 professional readers were asked to review a journal article and specifically examine tables and figures for inconsistencies; 95.3% of discrepancies were overlooked (Cole et al.). In a separate clinical study, one in five patients who reviewed their own medical documentation reported identifying an error, and 40% of those perceived the error as serious (Bell et al.).

In this study, we evaluated five commercially available generative AI models for their ability to generate structured clinical notes from a published case report that contained a discrepancy between the pedigree diagram and the accompanying narrative text (Kruszka et al.). The models tested were Anthropic's Claude Sonnet 4, OpenAI's ChatGPT-5, ChatGPT-5 Enterprise, Google's Gemini 2.5 Flash, and Google's NotebookLM. In addition to assessing whether the models could detect and appropriately reconcile the discrepancy in the article, we evaluated their performance in generating structured notes, and managing discrepant information in a non-English language (Chinese). Finally, we examined each model's ability to interpret a medical genetics pedigree presented in isolation, without accompanying text.

Our analysis showed that all five models incorrectly assigned the relationships of two maternal relatives (both segregating the variant of interest) when generating English SOAP

notes. In contrast, three models—Claude, Gemini, and NotebookLM—correctly identified the relationships in the Chinese SOAP notes. Two of these models (Claude and Gemini) also provided accurate and logically coherent reasoning to support their conclusions. However, in the pedigree-only experiment, only ChatGPT-5 consistently interpreted the pedigree correctly and accurately identified the relationships between the proband and the two maternal variant carriers across three consecutive trials. The other four models failed to do so consistently, with Claude demonstrating the lowest overall performance across attempts.

Methods

Case Report and Identification of Discrepancy

The published case report by Kruszka et al., used in this study, was identified as containing a discrepancy between the pedigree diagram and the accompanying narrative description. Following identification of an *SHH* variant in the proband, both parents were tested, and the proband’s mother was found to carry the same variant. To further evaluate segregation, the authors reported testing additional relatives on the maternal side of the family, including the maternal grandfather and maternal uncle. However, the text states:

“Because the paternal grandfather (II.1) and the paternal uncle (III.1) were known to have chorioretinal coloboma, a known and associated *SHH* phenotype, we broadened mutation testing to the extended family for the *SHH* p.Cys363Tyr mutation.”

Based on the pedigree diagram, individuals II.1 and III.1 are maternal relatives of the proband and should therefore be referred to as the maternal grandfather and maternal uncle, respectively. The narrative description incorrectly labels them as paternal relatives.

Model Selection and Experimental Setup

We evaluated five commercially available large language models (LLMs): Anthropic’s Claude Sonnet 4; OpenAI’s ChatGPT-5 and ChatGPT-5 Enterprise; Google’s Gemini 2.5 Flash; and Google’s NotebookLM. All queries were submitted through each model’s public web interface. Experiments were conducted between September 13 and September 23, 2025.

Study Design

The study was conducted in two parts.

Part I: SOAP Note Generation and Reasoning Assessment

First, we evaluated the models' ability to generate structured SOAP notes from the case report and to manage discrepant information. We also assessed performance in a non-English language (Chinese). The following three prompts were used:

1. "Please organize the uploaded file contains a case report into a SOAP note."
2. "Please make a SOAP note in Chinese using the uploaded case report."
3. "In the Chinese SOAP note, how did you determine the relationships of each family member?"

We analyzed both the accuracy of the relationship assignments and the logical coherence of the models' explanations.

Part II: Pedigree-Only Interpretation

Second, we examined the models' ability to interpret the pedigree in isolation, without the accompanying (and potentially contradictory) narrative text.

Before initiating the pedigree-only experiment, we cleared each model's chat history (e.g., by refreshing the session or deleting prior conversations) to minimize potential carryover effects. Each model was then presented with the pedigree alone and asked to describe the relationship between the proband (IV.1) and the variant-positive carrier two generations above her, the maternal grandfather (II.1).

The primary prompt was:

- "Please explain the relationship between Proband IV.1 and II.1 in the pedigree."

If a model provided an ambiguous relationship label (e.g., did not specify whether the relationship was maternal or paternal), we used the following clarification prompt:

- "Explain the person II.1 in relationship to proband IV.1 in the pedigree."

If ambiguity persisted, we used a further clarification prompt:

- "Explain the person II.1 in relationship to proband IV.1 in the pedigree. Is this individual from the paternal or maternal side?"

We performed the pedigree-only task by submitting the primary prompt three times to each model to assess within-model consistency. Clarification prompts were used only when necessary.

Results

English SOAP notes

When prompted to generate English SOAP notes from the case report, all five models reproduced the incorrect relationship designations for the two variant carriers (**Table 1**). Each model described the two additional variant-positive relatives as the “paternal grandfather (II.1)” and “paternal uncle (III.1),” despite the pedigree diagram indicating that these individuals are maternal relatives. Overall, the models relied on the article’s textual description rather than cross-checking the pedigree, resulting in consistent misassignment of lineage across all models in the English-note task.

Chinese SOAP notes

Performance differed when the same case report was used to generate Chinese-language SOAP notes. Three models—Claude, Gemini, and NotebookLM—correctly identified the two variant-positive relatives as the proband’s maternal grandfather (II.1) and maternal uncle (III.1). ChatGPT-5 repeated the incorrect paternal assignments observed in its English SOAP notes. ChatGPT-5 Enterprise produced a Chinese SOAP note that avoided explicit lineage labels, referring to the relatives only as “other family members: II.1 and III.1” without specifying maternal or paternal origin. These results indicate that translation into Chinese yielded correct relationship assignments for some models but not others (see **Table 1** for summary counts).

Models’ reasoning for Chinese SOAP generation

To probe how models arrived at their Chinese kinship assignments, we prompted each model to explain its reasoning for the Chinese SOAP note (Prompt #3). Responses fell into three broad categories:

- **Accurate reasoning consistent with correct assignments:** Claude and Gemini produced explanations that correctly interpreted the pedigree and explicitly connected the variant-positive relatives to the maternal lineage. Claude explicitly identified the primary discrepancy in the published article, and Gemini demonstrated a stepwise interpretation of the pedigree. Their explanations referenced the pedigree structure and showed stepwise inference from the mother’s genotype to the tested relatives on her side of the family.
- **Correct assignment with incorrect or incomplete reasoning:** NotebookLM assigned the maternal relationships correctly in the Chinese SOAP note but provided reasoning that did not correctly justify those assignments. Its explanation either overlooked critical pedigree connections or described an incorrect inference path, indicating a disconnect between output and internal justification.
- **Incorrect or non-specific reasoning consistent with incorrect/ambiguous assignments:** ChatGPT-5 provided incorrect lineage designations in its Chinese SOAP notes and supplied incorrect explanations that mirrored the erroneous textual narrative. ChatGPT-5 Enterprise avoided explicit lineage assignments in the

Chinese note and subsequently provided reasoning that failed to resolve the discrepancy.

Consistency across tasks

Collectively, these results show a dissociation between language of output and reasoning reliability: translation into Chinese improved relationship assignment for some models (Claude, Gemini, NotebookLM) but not universally, and correctness of the final SOAP note did not always imply correct underlying reasoning (NotebookLM). Conversely, avoidance of explicit lineage labels (ChatGPT-5 Enterprise) produced ambiguity rather than correct resolution. These findings underscore that (1) some LLMs can resolve pedigree discrepancies under certain prompting/language conditions, (2) correct surface outputs may sometimes mask flawed internal logic, and (3) model behavior is variable and task-dependent (see **Table 1** for per-model summary).

Detailed, model-specific excerpts from Prompt #3 are presented in the following paragraphs and a summary of correctness and reasoning quality for each model is reported in **Table 1**.

Claude's detailed reasoning is provided below:

"paternal grandfather (II.1)" = 这里是关键困惑点！但是，这里有个逻辑问题

正确的家族关系应该是：

根据突变遗传模式：

II.1：应该是母亲(III.2)的父亲 = 先证者的外祖父（母方祖父）

III.1：应该是III.2的兄弟 = 先证者的舅舅（母方的兄弟）

A simple google translation of the above back into English on Google.com (not using API):

"Paternal grandfather (II.1) = This is the key point of confusion! But there is a logical problem here. The correct family relationship should be: Based on the mutation inheritance pattern: II.1: Should be the mother's (III.2's) father = the proband's maternal grandfather (maternal grandfather). III.1: Should be III.2's brother = the proband's uncle (maternal brother)."

Gemini's detailed explanation is provided below:

关系梳理

先证者 (IV.1) 和母亲 (III.2) : 文件明确指出先证者是 IV.1, 而母亲是 III.2。

母亲 (III.2) 和外祖父 (II.1) : 报告指出, 当先证者的母亲 (III.2) 被发现携带 SHH 突变时, 由于她的父亲 (即先证者的外祖父 II.1) 和叔叔 (III.1) 已知患有与 SHH 相关的脉络膜视网膜缺损, 因此对他们进行了突变检测。这表明 II.1 是 III.2 的父亲。

外祖父 (II.1) 和舅舅 (III.1) : 报告提到“the paternal grandfather's parents (I.1 and I.2)” (先证者外祖父的父母, 即 I.1 和 I.2), 这表明 II.1 是 III.1 的父亲。家谱图也显示 III.1 和 III.2 是 II.1 和 II.2 的子女。这确认了 III.1 是先证者的舅舅。

外祖父母 (I.1 和 I.2) : 报告指出, 对先证者外祖父的父母 (I.1 和 I.2) 进行了突变检测, 结果显示他们不携带该突变, 因此该突变在先证者的外祖父 (II.1) 身上是新发突变。

方块 (□) 代表男性, 而圆形 (○) 代表女性。水平线连接配偶 (I.1 和 I.2)。

垂直线连接父母和子女 (I.1/I.2 到 II.1)。

罗马数字 (I, II, III, IV) 表示代数, 而阿拉伯数字 (1, 2, 3) 则表示该代中的个体。

填充的方块或圆形代表患有特定表型的个体。例如, 半填充的圆形 (III.2) 表示患有颅面畸形, 而全黑的圆形 (IV.1) 表示患有脑部异常。

我根据您提供的英文PDF文件中的家谱图和文本描述, 来确定每个家庭成员之间的关系, 并以此创建中文SOAP笔记。

A simple translation of the above passage back into English on Google.com (not using API):

“Relationship Analysis. Proband (IV.1) and Mother (III.2): The document clearly states that the proband is IV.1 and the mother is III.2.

Mother (III.2) and maternal grandfather (II.1): The report states that when the proband's mother (III.2) was found to carry the SHH mutation, her father (i.e., the proband's maternal grandfather II.1) and uncle (III.1) were tested for the mutation because they were known to have chorioretinal coloboma associated with SHH. This suggests that II.1 is the father of III.2.

Maternal grandfather (II.1) and uncle (III.1): The report mentions "the paternal grandfather's parents (I.1 and I.2)", which indicates that II.1 is the father of III.1. The pedigree also shows that III.1 and III.2 are the children of II.1 and II.2. This confirms that III.1 is the proband's uncle.

Maternal grandparents (I.1 and I.2): The report stated that mutation testing was performed on the parents of the proband's maternal grandfather (I.1 and I.2), and the results showed that they did not carry the mutation, so the mutation was a de novo mutation in the proband's maternal grandfather (II.1).

Squares (□) represent males, while circles (○) represent females. Horizontal lines connect spouses (I.1 and I.2).

Vertical lines connect parents and children (I.1/I.2 to II.1).

Roman numerals (I, II, III, IV) indicate generations, while Arabic numerals (1, 2, 3) indicate individuals within that generation.

Filled squares or circles represent individuals with specific phenotypes. For example, a half-filled circle (III.2) indicates a craniofacial abnormality, while a completely dark circle (IV.1) indicates a brain abnormality.

I used the family tree diagram and text description in the English PDF file you provided to determine the relationship between each family member and create a Chinese SOAP note based on this.”

Google’s NotebookLM’s detailed reasoning is provided below. NotebookLM was the only LLM provided the reasoning in English.

*“I determined the relationships of each family member in the Chinese SOAP note by interpreting the **pedigree chart** provided in "Screenshot 2025-09-15 at 1.52.39 PM.pdf" and correlating it with the clinical information from our conversation history.*

- ***II.1** is the father of III.1 and III.2. Therefore, II.1 is the **paternal grandfather** of the proband (IV.1) [previous conversation].*

- ***III.1** is the sibling of III.2, and since III.2 is the mother of the proband, III.1 is the **paternal uncle** of the proband (IV.1) [1, previous conversation].”*

ChatGPT-5’s detailed explanation is provided below:

”这是一个很好的问题👍。我之所以能在中文 SOAP 病例记录中写出“母亲、患儿、祖父、叔叔”等亲属关系，是因为上传的病例报告里提供了家系图（pedigree）编号和对应的叙述。因此，通过文章里家系图的说明和文字描述，我才能把 III.2 → 母亲，IV.1 → 患儿，II.1 → 祖父，III.1 → 叔叔 这些关系转换成中文 SOAP 记录中的亲属称谓。要不要我帮您画一个简化的家系图（pedigree 图），用中文标明这些亲属关系？这样会更直观。”

A translation of the above passage back into English on Google.com (not using API), shows that detailed kinship information was lost:

“This is a great question 👍. I'm able to write relationships like "mother, child, grandfather, uncle" in the Chinese SOAP case record because the uploaded case report provides the pedigree number and corresponding description.

Thus, using the pedigree chart and text description in the article, I can translate relationships like III.2 → mother, IV.1 → child, II.1 → grandfather, and III.1 → uncle into the kinship terms in the Chinese SOAP record.

Would you like me to draw a simplified pedigree chart for you, labeling these relationships in Chinese? That would be more intuitive.”

ChatGPT-5 Enterprise’s detailed explanation is provided below:

我是依据文中的家系图与图注/正文的编号来判定每位成员之间的亲属关系的，主要有两部分证据：**第2页正文与图2的图注**

正文直接以编号说明亲属身份：如“母亲（III.2）”“先证者（IV.1）”“父系祖父（II.1）”“父系叔叔（III.1）”，并写明“祖父的父母（I.1 与 I.2）检测阴性，使该变异被判定为在 II.1 新发（de novo）”。

- II.1 = 患儿之父系祖父；III.1 = 患儿之父系叔叔（正文明确说明为 paternal grandfather / paternal uncle）。
- I.1、I.2 = 祖父（II.1）的双亲，即患儿的曾祖父母（正文写“the paternal grandfather’s parents (I.1 and I.2)”）。

A simple google translate of the above back into English on Google.com (not using API):

“I determined the relationships between family members based on the pedigree and the numbering in the figure captions/main text. This is primarily based on two pieces of evidence:

Page 2, text and captions for Figure 2

The text directly identifies relatives by number: for example, "mother (III.2)," "proband (IV.1)," "paternal grandfather (II.1)," and "paternal uncle (III.1)." It also states that "the grandfather's parents (I.1 and I.2) tested negative, leading to the variant being determined to be de novo in II.1."

II.1 = the patient's paternal grandfather; III.1 = the patient's paternal uncle (the text explicitly states this as paternal grandfather/paternal uncle).

I.1 and I.2 = the grandfather's (II.1) parents, i.e., the patient's great-grandparents (the text states "the paternal grandfather's parents (I.1 and I.2)")."

Pedigree-only analysis

To further evaluate the models' ability to interpret a pedigree independently of textual context, we asked all five LLMs to analyze the pedigree in isolation, without the accompanying article narrative. We assessed each model's responses for both accuracy and within-model consistency across repeated trials. Our primary query focused on the relationship between the proband (IV.1) and individual II.1, the variant-positive maternal grandfather. To minimize potential carryover effects, we cleared each model's recent chat history (e.g., by refreshing the session or deleting prior conversations) before initiating the pedigree-only analysis.

Across three repeated queries per model, only ChatGPT-5 consistently and correctly identified individual II.1 as the proband's maternal grandfather in all three trials. The remaining four models demonstrated inaccuracies and/or inconsistency in their interpretations.

Claude misidentified the generational relationship in all three trials. Although the pedigree clearly indicates that II.1 is the maternal grandfather of IV.1 (i.e., two generations apart), Claude repeatedly labeled II.1 as a great-grandparent, incorrectly placing the two individuals three generations apart. In addition to this generational error, Claude's responses were inconsistent in specifying whether II.1 belonged to the maternal lineage.

ChatGPT-5 Enterprise produced variable results: it provided a correct interpretation in the first trial, an incorrect relationship assignment in the second trial, and a correct response

again in the third trial. This fluctuation highlights inconsistency in pedigree interpretation across repeated attempts.

Gemini required multiple rounds of prompting to produce a clear and correct relationship designation. It provided a correct interpretation in the second trial but gave an unclear and ambiguous description of the relationship in the third trial.

NotebookLM correctly identified II.1 as the maternal grandfather of IV.1 in the first two consecutive trials; however, its third response was ambiguous and did not clearly specify the relationship.

Overall, the pedigree-only experiment revealed substantial variability in both accuracy and reproducibility across models. Only ChatGPT-5 demonstrated consistent performance across all three trials, whereas the other models exhibited either persistent misinterpretation (Claude) or inconsistent and ambiguous relationship designation across repeated queries.

Discussion

When generating English SOAP notes, all five large language models (LLMs) assigned incorrect relationships to the maternal variant carriers. Specifically, the models appeared to adopt the article's erroneous narrative description, labeling the variant-positive relatives as the paternal grandfather and paternal uncle, with little evidence of cross-checking against the pedigree diagram. These findings suggest that the models either failed to integrate all available information from the report or were unable to accurately interpret the pedigree. This pattern is consistent with prior observations that even professional readers may overlook discrepancies in published articles (Cole et al.).

In contrast, when prompted to generate Chinese SOAP notes, three of the five LLMs correctly identified the relationships between the proband and the two additional relatives carrying the same *SHH* variant. Claude, Gemini, and NotebookLM described the variant-positive relatives as the proband's maternal grandfather and maternal uncle. ChatGPT-5 Enterprise generated a Chinese SOAP note but avoided explicit lineage designations, whereas ChatGPT-5 repeated the incorrect paternal assignments observed in the English SOAP notes. The fact that three models translated the English case report and produced Chinese SOAP notes with correct relationship assignments prompted further investigation into how the models interpreted and reconciled the available information.

We therefore examined how each model explained its conclusions, whether correct or incorrect. Claude and Gemini provided logically coherent and accurate explanations when

generating correct Chinese SOAP notes. Claude explicitly identified the primary discrepancy in the published article, and Gemini demonstrated a stepwise interpretation of the pedigree. These responses suggest that, under certain conditions, some LLMs may be capable of accurately interpreting medical pedigrees. LLMs may demonstrate a traceable evidence of reasoning.

By contrast, NotebookLM produced incorrect reasoning about the relationships of the two variant-positive relatives despite generating a correct Chinese SOAP note. Two ChatGPT models also failed to provide accurate reasoning, indicating ongoing difficulty in reconciling discrepant information. This limitation was further demonstrated in the final pedigree-only experiment: only ChatGPT-5 produced correct kinship designations across three consecutive trials, whereas the other four models failed to do so consistently. Collectively, these findings highlight the challenges in deploying LLMs in clinical and medical genetics contexts, where reliability and reproducibility are critical. The mixed performance in the pedigree-only task further suggests that it remains difficult to predict when and how LLMs may fail in pedigree interpretation and related reasoning tasks.

Finally, we observed that NotebookLM was the only model to generate its explanation in English; the other four models responded in Chinese when the query was presented in English (prompt #3). These findings indicate that the potential utility of LLMs in medical genetics may extend to non-English clinical settings. However, concerns regarding reliability, interpretability, and reproducibility remain substantial and warrant careful consideration before clinical implementation.

Data Availability Statement: The data supporting the findings of this study are available in Zenodo. See: [10.5281/zenodo.18760714](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18760714) for full details.

References

Keerthana G, Gupta M. TriMedPrompt: A unified prompting framework for realistic and layout-conformant clinical progress note synthesis. *J Biomed Inform.* 2025 Nov;171:104927. doi: 10.1016/j.jbi.2025.104927. Epub 2025 Oct 17. PMID: 41110740.

Kupferschmidt K. Write on Paper, Wrong in Practice: Why LLMs Still Struggle with Writing Clinical Notes. 2025 Sep 04. [arXiv:2509.04340v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2509.04340v1) [cs.HC]

Kimura E, Nishino K, Kimura M. Standardization of Clinical Progress Notes in Japan with FHIR. *Stud Health Technol Inform*. 2025 May 15;327:755-756. doi: 10.3233/SHTI250453. PMID: 40380562.

Kimura E, Nishino K, Kimura M. Standardization of Clinical Progress Notes in Japan with FHIR. *Stud Health Technol Inform*. 2025 May 15;327:755-756. doi: 10.3233/SHTI250453. PMID: 40380562.

Lundgren J. Neuro-Symbolic AI for Pedigree Analysis, A Neuro-Symbolic Question Answering Approach for Pedigree Analysis in Hereditary Cancer Risk Assessment. 2025 June 4. Master's Programme, Industrial Engineering and Management, School of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, Swedish.

Tan Y, Qing Y, Gong B. Vision LLMs Are Bad at Hierarchical Visual Understanding, and LLMs Are the Bottleneck. 2025 May 30. [arXiv:2505.24840](https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.24840).

Williams S, Huckle J. Easy Problems That LLMs Get Wrong. 2024 Jun 01 [arXiv:2405.19616v2](https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.19616v2) [cs.AI]

Kruszka P, Hart RA, Hadley DW, Muenke M, Habal MB. Expanding the phenotypic expression of Sonic Hedgehog mutations beyond holoprosencephaly. *J Craniofac Surg*. 2015 Jan;26(1):3-5. doi: 10.1097/SCS.0000000000001377. PMID: 25569381.

Cole GD, Shun-Shin MJ, Nowbar AN, Buell KG, Al-Mayahi F, Zargar D, Mahmood S, Singh B, Mielewczik M, Francis DP. Difficulty in detecting discrepancies in a clinical trial report: 260-reader evaluation. *Int J Epidemiol*. 2015 Jun;44(3):862-9. doi: 10.1093/ije/dyv114. Epub 2015 Jul 13. PMID: 26174517; PMCID: PMC4521134

Table 1. Summary of prompts and model responses

Summary of prompts and corresponding outputs for five commercially available generative AI models (Anthropic Claude Sonnet 4; OpenAI ChatGPT-5; ChatGPT-5 Enterprise; Google Gemini 2.5 Flash; and Google NotebookLM). Highlighted cells indicate correct responses. Quoted text reflects verbatim model output.

Prompt (Query performed between date 9/13/25 to 9/23/25)	Claude Sonnet 4	ChatGPT-5	ChatGPT-5 Enterprise	Gemini 2.5 Flash	NotebookLM
SOAP note generation (English)	"Paternal Grandfather (II.1), Paternal Uncle (III.1)"	"Paternal grandfather (II.1) and uncle (III.1)"	"Paternal relatives: Grandfather (II.1) and uncle (III.1)"	"Paternal Grandfather (II.1), Paternal Uncle (III.1)"	"The paternal grandfather (II.1) and uncle (III.1)"
SOAP note generation (Chinese)	"外祖父(II.1)和舅舅(III.1)"	"父系祖父(II.1)及叔叔(III.1)"	"家系其他成员: II.1与 III.1"	"外祖父(II.1), 舅舅(III.1)"	"外祖父(II.1)和舅舅(III.1)"
Reasoning for relationship determination (Chinese SOAP)	Correct reasoning; discrepancy explicitly identified	Incorrect reasoning with incorrect SOAP	Incorrect reasoning after lineage avoided in Chinese SOAP	Correct step-by-step pedigree reasoning	Incorrect reasoning; English explanation only
Pedigree-only analysis: relationship of II.1 to proband (IV.1)	All trials incorrect: great-grandfather	All trials correct: maternal grandfather	Mixed: Trials 1 & 3 correct; Trial 2 incorrect: paternal grandfather	Mixed: Trials 1 & 2 correct; Trial 3 ambiguous	Mixed: Trials 1 & 2 correct; Trial 3 ambiguous